

Abstract

A look on the evolution of life on Earth from a bigger perspective.

Evolution of life

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1 Intro

Evolution of life on the surface of Earth is, conventionally, not considered to be specifically scripted or having goals.

This is in contrast to its quanta, individuals or carriers of life, whose development from conception to adulthood is evidently coded. In these, the recipes for the building blocks are generally coded in DNA, while the development that starts with conception obviously has an effective goal - adulthood. That goal may be a consequence of chain reactions correlated with gradients of gene expression and synchronized self-organization of multiple entities, but the process does not deviate much from one individual of the species to the next. It appears that, once the process is triggered or initiated, unless the code or the process gets corrupted by external factors, as long as there's enough energy, the outcome is very predictable. Effectively, the process of development is coded as well, albeit in time.

In my theories, I argue that this coding in time is physical on some scale so the goals are real on that scale, not just effective. One can think of the goals as hallucinations and the *final* goal is a superposition of intermediate hallucinations. Obviously, these hallucinations also evolve over time, but during development of the individual the influence of the body components on them may be negligible. The *intermediate* or localized hallucinations guide the development of tissues while the superposition orchestrates or synchronizes these developments. Effectively, hallucinations represent gradients in certain field potentials so the guidance through time is similar to guidance of ordinary matter in a gravitational well of dark matter. In another interpretation, hallucination is a force, affecting living components, such as cells, on a subconscious level. What may then be interpreted as spontaneous self-organization, is relatively spontaneous, on some scale it is scripted. Entanglements have an influence as well. We might be accustomed to correlating effects or strength of effects with spatial distance, however, entangled entities may be spatially separated but localized in time.

If there is guidance on the small scale, why there wouldn't be guidance on larger scales? I argue that hallucinations exist on various scales and, just like cells are guided to form a specific organ or microbes to form a biofilm, complex animals are guided as well into *spontaneous* self-organization. Some of these organizations are temporary (note that even in the standard embryonic development temporary organizations exist), some may converge to something bigger, and, overall, on various levels of subconscious all or most of complex life on Earth's surface may be guided toward the formation of an relative organ or an organism of a larger scale.

Evolution is thus equivalent with development and individual development may be interpreted as a quantum of evolution.

As I postulate in Complete Relativity[1] (CR), all forms of energy must oscillate and life is not an exception.

After conception, life-forms in general grow to peak size and then start shrinking, die and decay. Life of any individual is thus a pulse of energy and, with the introduction of a reincarnating soul, it is an oscillating form of energy.

This oscillation evolves, and here it is hypothesized that, over large scale periods, life oscillates in complexity (intelligence) between dominantly introverted and dominantly extroverted nature or between expression of introverted and extroverted mechanics. This is thus the exchange of complexity between physical and mental abilities, assuming extroverted expression is dominantly physical, introverted dominantly mental. Evolution may proceed in either dominantly progressive or dominantly regressive manner between adjacent vertical energy levels, even though progression and regression are both relative.

2 Everything is alive

As I have hypothesized previously[2], symbiosis of organisms, with a pulse of strong evolution, becomes a symbiosis of organs with (previously) mental connections *fossilized* into tissue connecting organs, now forming a new unique organism.

Similarly, symbiosis of single cells (single-celled organisms) effectively forming a single organism, with a pulse of strong evolution, *formally* becomes a unique multi-cellular organism.

UPDATE: Recent research shows that "biofilm formation in *Bacillus* is a bona fide developmental process comparable to organismal development in animals, plants, and fungi"[3].

In a symbiosis of single-celled organisms, different organisms take different roles - some specialize for feeding, some for reproduction, etc. These specialized cells are thus organ precursors.

Obviously, nature is repeating its mechanics on discrete scales. So, why should this scale invariance be limited only to two scales?

Comparing the Solar System with the atom[4], obviously, it is not.

Thus, even a single-celled organism must be a multi-celled organism, it's just not have been, by modern science, recognized as such yet.

Comparing [the order of] size of a typical organ and an eukaryotic cell, one obtains the ratio:

$$\frac{10 \text{ cm}}{10 \mu\text{m}} = \frac{0.1 \text{ m}}{10 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}} = 10000$$

With non-dimensional ratios invariant to scale, size of cells forming an eukaryotic cell then must be:

$$\frac{10 \mu\text{m}}{10000} = \frac{10 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}}{10000} = 1 * 10^{-9} \text{ m}$$

Size of cells forming a prokaryotic cell:

$$\frac{1 \mu\text{m}}{10000} = \frac{1 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}}{10000} = 1 * 10^{-10} \text{ m}$$

For the smallest prokaryotic cells:

$$\frac{0.1 \mu\text{m}}{10000} = \frac{0.1 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}}{10000} = 1 * 10^{-11} \text{ m}$$

The size of cells forming eukaryotic cells is thus on the order of size of molecules, while for prokaryotic cells it is on the order of size of atoms.

Obviously, a molecule is an organism formed by the strong symbiosis of atoms, atoms are living cells, and they must contain even smaller cells.

Note that an atom nucleus is 10000 times smaller than the atom.

If an atom is a living cell, a planetary system is a living cell - something I have already shown elsewhere.

A previously hypothesized planetary neurogenesis, in which life on the surface evolves into equivalents of neuron cells and proteins for the brain of the planet, is thus a logical step in its evolution.

3 Prelude

In CR, a gravitational well is generally associated with a distinct gravitational maximum. Distinct form of life begins its development with the acquisition of real mass by a [naked] gravitational maximum (soul).

In an example - a planet has a distinct maximum and is thus a distinct form of life, an small asteroid is probably usually not a distinct form of life but a distinct collective of introverted, living atomic cells.

Asteroids may be fragments of dead bodies and can provide energy for [the development of] living planets.

However, even though I use the terms *gravitational well* and *gravitational maximum* even for souls coupling to bodies of animals on Earth, dominant force is not always gravity.

In general, it is the entanglement between different scales of energy that is involved in soul/body coupling. This can be correlated with excitations of, and gradients in, certain field potentials, but the nature of these may vary.

A soul may generally start its new incarnation in a two-dimensional (polarized) form. In case of an inner (terrestrial) planet, the maximum is probably extracted from the star (which is initially bigger) as a two-dimensional ring of electric charge (a charged large scale graviton).

This may be generally initiated when an outer planet (eg. electron equivalent) is attracted to the system nucleus, either in the process of fusion or neutralization of an ionized system.

With the attraction, magnetic spins of the soul quantum of the system nucleus and the outer planet are anti-aligned and these are attracted.

In the beginning, neutral force (gravity) of the maximum was low - most energy was in the spin momentum and electro-magnetic in nature.

The non-homogeneous magnetic field was channelling the plasma from the Sun toward the poles and then about the maximum, as there was no atmosphere and no matter to stop it - the Sun was feeding the Earth.

The plasma (mainly protons and electrons) was confined to the oscillation on the equator by electric and magnetic fields, with an orbital momentum opposing the magnetic field of the maximum.

At the same time this system is orbiting the Sun, attracting (at first, metallic) dust and clumps of matter from the protoplanetary field, while the maximum is collapsing, when finally the electro-magnetic spin momentum fragments into smaller moon quanta of the maximum.

During the collapse, the two-dimensional ring maximum is transforming into a neutral gravitational sphere (surface).

As for the heavy elements, there are two possibilities, depending on initial energy. If it was comparable or lower than current total mass of the Earth, all heavy elements must have come from the protoplanetary disks, asteroids and comets. However, if the Sun was initially bigger, the collapse or localization of the Earth's maximum could have been much more energetic, even allowing fusion of elements. If one calculates gravity for a point mass equal to Earth's total mass, this gravity is equal to the surface gravity of the Sun (274 m/s^2) at the radius of Earth's inner core. Is this a coincidence? Probably not, but

different interpretations are possible. In one interpretation, the initial graviton energy was equal to current total Earth mass and the mass was concentrated on a ring (or sphere surface) of the graviton (with radius roughly equal to the current Earth's inner core radius), while the real mass (ordinary matter) was created afterwards with annihilation of dark matter, energy associated with the graviton.

In another interpretation, initial graviton mass is low ($2 \times 6.95 \times 10^{19}$ kg[5]) and remains constant during Earth's formation and development but its spin momentum is decreased and at the end such that spin velocity becomes Keplerian velocity at the radius roughly equal to current inner core radius, for an enclosed mass equal to graviton mass. And this radius is such that the gravity would be equal to $2 \times 137 = 274$ m/s² for an enclosed mass equal to total mass after formation (consequence of entanglement with the Sun).

If annihilation of dark matter was involved, or the initial energy was significantly greater than current total mass, the collapse may have involved [a process equivalent to] fusion of elements so at least some, if not most, of the heavy elements could have been created *in situ*. This scenario will be described next.

Since the maximum is not a point maximum, fusion products (mostly lighter atoms) are getting ejected through the poles until the poles close.

The fusion products are equal to the products of Sun like star fusion products over its lifetime - proton-proton chain reactions, followed by triple- α and C-N-O cycles.

The elements ejected through the poles are thus the unspent hydrogen (H) fuel and the stable fusion products - mainly carbon (C), nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O).

Note that H, C, N, and O are the base elements of amino acids.

Heaviest elements produced in the collapse are iron (Fe), nickel (Ni) and, in smaller amounts, cobalt (Co). Most of these elements were left trapped inside to form the core of the Earth.

The ejected elements possibly collide at the equator eventually, but first react with the primal energetic hydrogen atmosphere engaging in covalent bonds and forming gases - water vapour (H₂O), methane (CH₄) and ammonia (NH₃). These gases now form the early atmosphere of Earth.

At this time the Earth is also bombarded with asteroids and, possibly, comets. In the turbulent atmosphere with frequent electric discharges, amino acids and peptides are created.

Some organic *stimulants* may have come from meteors, but some, such as phosphides, are also created locally with electric discharges.

Soon the Earth is filled with oceans. With high volcanic activity, hydrothermal vents are abundant.

All of this is probably as scripted as human embryonic development, and first cells were destined to form from atoms and molecules.

Note that Earth, as a quantum particle, is hypothesized to be in 2e configuration - a composition of 2 fused souls (gravitational maximuma). In one interpretation, these are carbon souls, and each carbon soul, apart from the core (major, or central) maximum, contains 6 additional quanta. The additional maxima are grouped into quantum shells (s, p, d, f, ..). For ^{12}C soul, there are 2 quanta in 1s shell, 2 in 2s shell, 2 in 2p shell separated into $2p_1$ and $2p_2$ sub-shells. There are thus 4 groups, potentially forming 4 moons of the core maximum. In case of a covalent bond of 2 carbon souls, the 2s and 2p shells hybridize into a single shell, giving a total of 6 moons between two binary cores. When these fuse, two cores are in 2e configuration (forming inner and outer core) and 6 moons are now orbiting a single soul (planet). However, the Earth is itself a moon maximum of another larger soul (Sun's soul) and under such pressure the 6 moons (which are all fermion pairs and thus bosonic) will again pair up to form 4 moons. The evolution of Earth is thus equal to the evolution of Mars and Venus, even though these are in 1e configuration.

4 Interlude

The Earth may have had 4 moons in the beginning. These may be interpreted as its vital organs.

However, its progressive evolution leads to complete introversion, so these were/are destined to fuse with Earth (homo.omega individual).

Similar to *fossilization* of symbiosis of multiple organisms into organs of a single organism, symbiosis or organs will, in progressive evolution, fuse to form layers of a single organ[ism].

Complete introversion is characterized by the spherical structure, lack of physical limbs and externally expressed organs.

However, this is certainly not the case during the whole period of ontogenesis. In the beginning, the form is not spherical and even the individuals of omega species have multiple organs.

The openings on the poles are effectively mouth of the species and opened tubes are intestines, although one opening probably eventually differentiates into waste exit. Other organs also appear briefly in some form during development.

In adults of such species, the only significantly evolved organ is the brain (although the core of the brain itself may be considered as the equivalent of a heart), so ontogenesis is roughly *reduced* to neurogenesis.

Note that, here, adult form is reached at the end of embryonic neurogenesis.

The mantle of Earth is thus the brain mantle of Earth and it has 6 layers separated by discontinuities (which may represent minor soul quanta and/or discrete energy levels for the soul) just like our brains.

The process of neurogenesis, population of these layers with neurons is something I have described in details elsewhere so I will not go into details here.

In progressive evolution, periodic strong evolution pulses initiate effective fusion of cells, while, in between the pulses, cells are dividing and diverging - increasing population.

The cells are initially atoms, then molecules, followed by single-celled and multi-celled organisms.

During strong evolution pulses, the maximum collapse (expansion) is correlated with the temporary mouth recreation or opening (roughly at the south pole, on Earth) and recreation or reactivation of tunnels leading to mantle layers. At major mass *extinction* events, this lasts sufficiently long to allow migration of neuron cells to designated mantle layers.

The product of fusion of human genomes (homo.sapiens) may form the proteins residing in neuron cells correlated with higher cognition.

Since such neuron cells occupy specific layers of the Earth's brain it is reasonable to assume that cultivation of homo began after the last (5th) major extinction, 66 million img years ago (61.986 million real years ago, per the hypothesis of effective time compression). Thus, evolution of homo is not a coincidence, rather scripted as standard embryonic development of neural cells.

Real years or real time is a period of time adjusted for the compression of time with strong evolution pulses. Imaginary (img) time represents uncompressed (uniformitarian) time, not adjusted for these pulses.

During weak evolution (occurring between pulses of strong evolution), size of the individual of cultivated species is growing exponentially by natural doubling time law. Size is thus doubling in regular constant intervals, until the

fundamental limit is reached. After this peak, a *fundamental* change is required in order for evolution to continue progressively.

Generally, this change is not immediate and some regression has to occur before it occurs.

Doubling time is applied to many phenomena in nature, such as population growth, volume of malignant tumours and decay rate of isotopes. It is also the basis of Moore's law.

This is why major mass extinctions are relative extinctions - life is extinct relative to surface only, it is actually transformed and transferred to another location where it can continue its weak evolution.

The equation for (cell) size doubling time is:

$$N(t) = N(0)2^{t/T_d} \tag{1.1}$$

$N(t)$ = size at time t

$N(0)$ = initial size

T_d = doubling period (time it takes for size to double)

t = time

The equation for (cell) population doubling time is (for growth rate equal to $1/T_d$):

$$N(t) = N(0)e^{t/T_d} \tag{1.2}$$

If one applies these equations to homo evolution, assuming negative population growth rate (with increase in individual size, population decreases), with initial size equal to modern human radius and population equal to human population, at $t = 23 T_d$ size of the homo cell reaches Earth radius and population becomes equal to 1.

Here, 7.8 billion was used as initial population and 0.66 m as initial size (radius) of the individual.
I have defined human radius before[6] so I will not go into details here.

At $t = 43 T_d$, U_1 .carbon.atom (Solar System) size is reached.

If one now applies equations to past evolution (negative size growth rate, positive population growth rate), at $t = -23 T_d$ size is equal to smallest prokaryotic cell, at $t = -33 T_d$ it is equal to standard (U_0) carbon atom size, and at $t = -46 T_d$ it reaches [classical] electron (positron) size.

One can calculate standard positron radius from radii of Earth, Neptune and standard carbon atom.

Standard (U_0) positron in this context is the Earth equivalent in a standard carbon atom. Its radius can be obtained from these relations:

$$\frac{R_{E_1}}{r_{E_1}} = \frac{R_{E_0}}{r_{E_0}}$$

$$\frac{r_{N_1}}{r_{E_1}} = \frac{r_{N_0}}{r_{E_0}}$$

$$R_{E_1} = U_1.\text{Earth [spin] radius} = 6371000 \text{ m}$$

$$R_{E_0} = U_0.\text{Earth [spin] radius}$$

$$r_{E_1} = U_1.\text{Earth orbital radius} = 149.6 * 10^9 \text{ m}$$

$$r_{E_0} = U_0.\text{Earth orbital radius}$$

$$r_{N_1} = U_1.\text{Neptune orbital radius} = 4495.06 * 10^9 \text{ m}$$

$$r_{N_0} = U_0.\text{Neptune orbital radius} = 70 * 10^{-12} \text{ m}$$

where U_0 .Neptune orbital radius is equal to standard carbon atom radius. Substitution gives:

$$R_{E_0} = R_{E_1} \frac{r_{N_0}}{r_{N_1}} = 6.371 * 10^6 \text{ m} * 1.557 * 10^{-23} = 9.92 * 10^{-17} \text{ m}$$

This size is reached at $t = -53 T_d$.

Note however that spin radius oscillates with mass, so if Earth in this state has a d quark equivalent mass, standard positron radius is 10 times smaller and it is reached at $t = -55 T_d$.

This is illustrated and mapped to evolution of nature of intelligence (introverted/extroverted ratio) on Fig. 1.

Notice that modern human (homo.beta) is exactly at 2/3 between U_0 .carbon.e and U_1 .carbon.e:

$$\frac{\log_2(2^{46})}{\log_2(2^{46}) + \log_2(2^{23})} = \frac{2}{3}$$

Hypothesized fundamental change will occur with the strong evolution pulse, transforming homo.beta into homo sapiens. From that point onwards, progressive evolution will have to start doubling the size of the host (Earth) in order to continue evolution of the smaller scale homo (sapiens).

Note that once size of the host starts doubling, neuron cells of sapiens will be fusing too, so the number of neurons remains constant.

This will remain so until sapiens (more precisely, its descendant) leaves homo.omega and settles in an environment with higher relative fundamental population limit, when doubling continues.

This should happen with iteration no. 22, so with iteration no. 23,

Figure 1: Homo evolution (distances not to scale)

homo.sapiens evolves into homo.omega.

But how long is the doubling time T_d ?

I have previously hypothesized that, apart from periodic extinctions (period ≈ 26 million years on average), there are pulses of existence (weaker evolution pulses) with a period of 1.512 million years. I believe T_d is equal to this period.

Note that ≈ 1.5 million years ago human brain size was half of its present size. It is also the time when humans started using fire. About this time homo.habilis went extinct and it's height was at least roughly equal to half of the height of modern human. This is all in agreement not only with a 1.5 My period of size doubling, but agrees with the hypothesis of a 3rd order period of 1.5 My (associated with smaller extinctions) - assuming we are currently in the midst of an extinction.

If cultivation of humans had to begin after the last major extinction, as hypothesized, with $T_d = 1.512$ million years, this is fulfilled at $t = -43 T_d$ (65.016 Ma).

Note that, for the same t , equation 1.2 gives population roughly equal to the number of atoms inside a human body.

However, while T_d of 1.512 My is plausible for body size doubling, it is obviously not in agreement with population size doubling - human population was recently doubling every 47 years not every 1.5 million years.

But note also that this doubling period is not constant - it has shortened significantly over the last couple of centuries. One can thus assume that this pulse of explosion of population [designated for transfer] occurs at the end of every 3rd order period and is followed by a sharp decline. The hypothesized pulses of strong (accelerated) evolution with the end of these periods imply acceleration of population growth too, thus resolving the discrepancy. This implies that the population of homo.habilis numbered about 4 billion (or 16 billion for inverse relation to body size) at its peak (current human population is likely to peak at about 8 billion, which will be reached 2023 - 2040, depending on the rate of growth decay).

Due to cataclysmic nature, decline after the peak is likely significantly sharper than the rise before it.

Time $t = -23 T_d$ (34.776 Ma), when size reaches the size of a prokaryotic cell, can also be associated with a mass extinction event (Eocene-Oligocene, Popigai impactor).

If cultivation had to begin less than 66 Ma, most certainly it did not start with a cell size smaller than the size of electron. However, more likely minimum is the size of the atom and most likely minimum is the size of a prokaryotic or eukaryotic cell (if life has to start over after an extinction it probably won't start with a smaller cell if bigger cells survived).

Doubling time T_d must satisfy this condition. Chosen T_d of 1.512 million years satisfies, supporting not only prokaryotic cells but atoms ($t = -33 T_d = 49.896$ Ma) too for the minimum size.

4.1 Scaling of mass

Mass obviously does not scale proportionally to 2^n , rather 10^n . However, it obviously oscillates during evolution. This is shown in Table 1, where m_0 is roughly equal to average human mass. There is a remarkable agreement between 10^n mass scaling and 2^n radius scaling for n equal to -23, 0 and 23. However, apparently, large discrepancies are present elsewhere - eg. for $n = 43$, radius is roughly equal to Solar System radius, while mass is equal to the mass of a

n	species	mass (kg)	$10^n m_0$ (kg)
-23	standard protein	$\approx 10^{-22}$	$6 * 10^{-22}$
0	homo.beta	60	60
23	homo.omega	$\approx 6 * 10^{24}$	$6 * 10^{24}$
43	Solar System / carbon black hole?	$\approx 2 * 10^{30}$	$6 * 10^{44}$

Table 1: Mass scaling

galaxy.

This is not surprising if one correlates radius and mass with orbital radii and mass of particles in atoms. As shown in Solar System analysis, particles may oscillate horizontally between energy levels (changing orbital radius), but masses in the system can oscillate significantly with no significant changes in orbital radii.

Thus, species for $n = 43$ may not be the U_1 carbon isotope (Solar System), rather a system (black hole) with a mass radius smaller than its [standard] event horizon (Schwarzschild radius).

Note that for $n = -55$, when radius is equal to likely standard positron radius in a carbon atom, mass becomes $6 * 10^{-54}$ kg, in good agreement with standard photon or half photon mass obtained in recent experiments[7].

Note however that all these masses are relative to an absolute frame of reference where photon speed is limited to $c = c_0 = 2.99792458 * 10^8$ m/s. In CR, proper photon mass is on the order of 10^{-72} kg. As mass oscillation [between discrete vertical energy levels] conserves momentum, scaling of mass should be correlated with *rest* velocity:

$$10^n m_0 v_0 = m_n v_n$$

$$m = m_n = 10^n m_0 \frac{v_0}{v_n}$$

$$v_n < c_n$$

4.2 Polarization of evolution

Obviously, evolution between small scale and large scale life is not only the exchange of complexity, but a change in polarization. The nature of interactions evolves between a polarized (electro-magnetic) and non-polarized gravitational character.

While direction of evolution is relative, from our perspective, progressive evolution is the transition from electro-magnetic to gravitational interactions.

The magnetic field of Earth has been decreasing in strength from its beginnings. Even when its nature changed with the formation of the inner core, it had to be generally decreasing with each major mass extinction.

At first, decrease is correlated with the formation of mantle layers. With the addition of another layer, the magnetic field strength on surface has to decrease.

Afterwards, it is correlated with neuron migration to these layers - more energy is needed to populate deeper layers.

Precursor neuron cells and proteins cultivated during Earth's neurogenesis should somehow reflect the extinction of polarization. Since binary characteristics - sex and gender, evolve from magnetic spin and chirality, polarization should thus be reflected in sexual dimorphism of such species. While physical and mental differences are generally synchronized, on smaller time scales one may be considered as the precursor of the other.

This decrease in dimorphism is evident in evolving males and females of human species, but also between modern humans and its ancestors (dimorphism is much larger in other hominoids).

Since human evolution (as part of embryonic development of Earth) is mirrored in human embryogenesis, this dimorphism should be largest at the time of conception of human life. Evidently, it is - with female ovum being the largest cell of the human body and male sperm being the smallest.

Note that fusion of these cells into a zygote (new life-form) is an event of strong evolution of species on small scale. It shows that in the event of extinction (most sperm cells die), some of the cells fuse into new species (in this case, generally, only two - Adam and Eve precursors) and are transferred (as an *egg*) to another location (mother's uterus, which now forms the shell of the *egg*) where this new life can continue evolving.

After the transfer, cell divides into two - male and female (real Adam and Eve), but this time with minimal dimorphism, such that reproduction is further driven by mitosis.

Yes, many events in the bible are based on science but heavily corrupted - in this case, equality of man and woman was sacrificed to make men superior. So the god too was made male, even though the gods can be female too. By my definition of god, after birth, our first god becomes Earth, a male (again, by my definition, correlated with spin), but at the time of conception, first god to anyone of us is female (our mother). Not only that, but everyone of us is female before conception, as the spin of a naked soul should probably be anti-aligned with the spin of the Earth's graviton.

With self-similarity (relative scale invariance), obviously the process of neurogenesis is relatively equal to genesis - it includes extinction, fusion and migration. The difference is only in the ratio of extinct to fused (transformed) individuals, which should be proportional to sexual dimorphism. Thus, each larger extinction event may be interpreted as the event of fertilization and likely fusion, but only in major extinction events it is completely *successful* - resulting in migration.

In the current, 6th major extinction, homo.beta (a species of homo currently inhabiting Earth's surface) is a precursor to homo.sapiens, species described in *The species of homo*[8]. In the same paper, the mechanism of large (Earth) scale fusion of gametes is also described.

5 Postlude

After the completion of neurogenesis, the planet is fully developed and reaches the adult stage. There is no more cultivation of cells (complex life) on surface. All life is underground, concentrated about the discontinuities of brain mantle layers (although a possibility exists for occasional limited reappearance of surface life as part of adult neurogenesis).

Note that this is the major reason why projects like SETI didn't yet reveal any intelligent civilizations in the observable universe - the period of time an externally advanced civilization (capable of emission of radio waves into outer space) spends on the surface of a planet is extremely short.

Reason why life appears on the surface during development is due to dependence on external energy for that development - afterwards it becomes self-sustainable.

Life on surface is vulnerable to small scale (radiation) and large scale impacts. So in order to remain preserved, it is logical for life to move deep below surface where it is protected from such phenomena.

Note that the atmosphere of a planet provides some protection, both from radiation and meteorites. It is an imaginary mantle, a precursor to real, protection providing, mantle and bone layer.

Along with the missing magnetic dipole, the inhospitable atmospheres of Mars and Venus indicate these are completely formed, adult planets.

While atmospheres of some moons of outer planets suggest life forms in formation, these are lower energy organs (different species) and will not evolve as far as Earth. In fact, the absence of a dipole indicates their formation is complete too.

There is no more growth, population of living cells is stable and all life lives in a sustainable way.

Evolution is weak, until soul of Earth fuses with a soul from another U_1 atom.

Note that the whole observable universe is contained within a discontinuity (soul maximum, event horizon) of a larger scale brain[9]. All the galaxies, their interactions and connections (dark matter filaments) are a reflection of large scale life around that discontinuity.

Everything, is alive.

The fact that 3/4 of observable universe is of extremely low density (dark energy) instead of being filled with U_1 scale water reveals that it is not the actual brain but its, mass inverted, reflection.

This is thus another evidence for the existence of a soul. It also shows that the soul is evolving with the body, as hypothesized.

Since observable universe is a part of a large scale gravitational maximum, one now knows what gravitational maximum (event horizon) looks like and since one knows this particular one is the soul of a brain, comparing it to our brain, one can say a lot about its development and evolution.

The observable universe did not start from an infinitely small and infinitely dense point of space-time. It did experience a period of inflation (rapid growth), it's not going to be expanding and cooling forever (with photons having mass, as CR requires, it's questionable whether it is expanding even now), it might change spin and collapse (upon death) or fuse with another soul and start evolving again (in fact, if the expansion is indeed accelerating, this would indicate the upcoming fusion).

Obviously, if this discontinuity is reflecting a brain of a larger scale, it also has to have a relative radius and spin/orbital momentum. It is thus not only the evidence for the existence of a soul, but it completely validates the postulates of CR.

5.1 The symphony and its harmony in imitation of gods

Evolving between two life forms at stable (discrete) energy levels, intermediate life forms are both nothing and all but *virtual* particles popping in and out of existence, imitating one or the other.

In its essence, evolution of life is a journey through a wormhole of entanglement between two atoms of different scale.

It truly is a symphony of sound in [slowed down] light, a symphony of creation and destruction.

A life in harmony is thus life in diversity.

But how many times life starts from the *beginning*?

It is well known that embryonic development of all species starts roughly the same and diversifies later into particular species, but even during that compressed time it oscillates in form of [symbiosis of] species it evolved from.

Growth of a body, with intensifying symbiosis between organs is simultaneous with the inflation of a soul, so the question of beginning is the question of scale of that soul at the time it couples with a body.

There is no question that soul between deaths and births travels relatively naked. As such, it travels at the speed of *light*, but is it the speed of *light* on U_0 (c) or U_1 scale (c_1)?

Is it thus the scale [species] of an ^{10}Be atom, or the scale of a ^{10}C photon, or ^{10}B neutrino/anti-neutrino pair (a more progressively evolved photon)?

I believe life starts [inflating] at the smallest scale it can be aware of, it is thus the scale of photon components or, rarely (at this point), neutrinos.

There is another reason why the soul of *standard* creatures [such as humans] has to be of lower scale than the scale of standard atoms.

Consciousness is a quantum phenomena, which, generally, requires strong condensation (localization of energy levels) conforming to Bose-Einstein statistics.

Such condensates are stable only at extremely low temperatures or densities. Matter of standard scale in the brain is simply too dense and too hot to provide a suitable environment for bosonic condensation of standard particles.

Considering that particles on U_1 scale are stable condensates (observable universe is of extremely low [properly scaled] density), while living matter of standard (U_0) scale operates on *room* temperature, most likely, the inversion of natural operation, as I have hypothesized previously, occurs between any adjacent vertical energy levels.

Thus, one can expect conditions of U_1 scale to be mirrored on U_0 (photon mass) scale (indeed, photons are bosonic on standard room temperature). Note that, with consciousness being the expression of quantum condensates, it becomes rather trivial to explain dreams and *out-of-body* experiences.

In a certain way, these experiences are fake - they are rendered based on information delivered by distant worlds (either in scale and/or space-time) one's world is entangled with, so it might seem inappropriate to refer to them as being experienced in reality rather than simulated (although, either one is *very* scripted).

However, strength of entanglement is proportional to similarity between the worlds (individuals), so there is a high probability the environment and interactions in these experiences will be very similar to ones in the world of material residence.

Note that some distance in time will always exist between synchronized (entangled) worlds, making it possible for one to effectively experience the lives of its past or future incarnations.

If that distance is large, there may be some trouble in rendering (eg. in producing appropriate visuals, hormone reactions) as this is based on experiences in space/time of material residence.

For instance, [in a dream] one may feel as driving a vehicle but the visuals of vehicle interior may be missing (as I myself have experienced), indicating a likely shift in time and that this vehicle must be very different than those one drives in current incarnation.

I do not believe that soul needs a brain *per se* for expression of consciousness and memory storage, but its self likely has to be localized (condensed), otherwise it becomes impossible to correlate and focus information to a particular sense.

Such operation is suggested by dreams (visions or retro-visions) of death experiences. Note that a brain is a learning machine and once it learns how to combine past experiences and knowledge to generate new content it may preferably generate dreams locally rather than interpret received signals. In what measure the content of a dream was an experienced (real) or fake (virtual) reality will thus depend on the individual. Probability for real visions should thus be generally higher in younger children. Among adults, probability should be higher in unbiased brains, which is the state brains of non-polarized humans (neutralums) are most often in. Obviously, we do not only possess the set of sensory organs (sensors) we are familiar with but there is a mirror of these, sensing probable past and future experiences.

Generally, one set is subdued during daily operation, the other is subdued during sleep, but neither can be completely shut down.

Note that synchronicity and its guidance to future show that environment of the individual is, at least at times, also entangled with the same worlds.

Surely, additional souls can be absorbed during lifetime, but is that *permanent*?

In my example, about the age of 36 something has definitely changed with my soul and I became a different person.

I will generally use singular form when referring to the primary soul coupled with a particular body. However, as Earth is in 2e configuration and human souls are part of Earth's space, human souls should also be in 2e configuration - composites of 2 soul quanta.

Have I, thus, at the age of 36, temporarily absorbed another soul (gravita-

tional wave maximum) which triggered inflation of one constituent soul quantum (eg. anti-neutrino with dominant *Newton* personality) and deflation of the other soul quantum (eg. neutrino with *Jesus* personality) or have I absorbed a new soul (anti-neutrino) and, consequently, extended lifetime to 120 years?

Since I haven't noticed my body growing, I believe such absorption is temporary and only acts as a trigger for inflation/deflation of already coupled soul quanta between different energy levels.

The temporary absorption here is likely not the absorption of the soul that was in another body, rather a quantum emitted with the collapse (death) of a soul. However, due to self-similarity, this quantum is an equivalent (image) of the larger soul.

Note that bodies and souls co-evolve so the probability for coupling is greater when difference in evolution is smaller, except with entanglement at larger distances where, due to flavour oscillation a soul can couple even with different species, although, if one is significantly entangled with different species during lifetime, probability for flavour oscillation increases even at small distance.

Due to requirement of similarity in coupling, emitted soul quanta after death might temporarily couple with a soul of a close relative which will additionally trigger inflation/deflation of soul quanta of that relative.

I have noticed people do start changing after death of relatives. I believe death of the father of my ex wife was synchronized with deflation of chances of sustaining our marriage.

I believe my mother has temporarily absorbed the soul quantum emitted with the death of her father, which temporarily inflated the expression of his genes and permanently changed her afterwards.

This also happened at the time of my own transformation so the same soul might be *responsible* for changing both me and my mother. My father is also a different person now, although his state was most likely altered by some other soul. Such soul interactions should thus be common and normal part of evolution.

That imitation of gods starts early in life is evident through the comparison of an egg with Earth or a bound positron equivalent.

In the analysis of the Solar System, I have concluded that the primary or primordial source of Earth's magnetic dipole is the concentrated charge in Earth's inner core.

This is shown on Fig. 2.

Initially, one soul (maximum) acts as a precursor of crust and another of a source of energy (core).

From the initial moment of creation (inflation) this universe starts imitating itself. Acquired mass, due to intrinsic rotation and applied heat, creates a charge equivalent above the matter event horizon (mass maximum) creating a magnetic

Figure 2: Initialization of life

dipole equivalent of initial charge.

With the presence of a magnetic field the outer energy level (maximum) splits into 6 quanta and acquired mass is being distributed and concentrated in between, imitating the maximum - acquisition of mass stops once real mass becomes equal to the mass of the maximum.

Compare 6 layers of Earth's mantle with 6 layers of your brain mantle, compare your brain to galaxies connected with dark matter filaments.

Compare then the splitting of living cells to splitting of maximums, fusion and fission of atoms to fusion and fission of cells. This never ends, it just oscillates, so, over all time, it is impossible to tell who is imitating who - sometimes the body (acquired mass) will imitate the soul (maximum), sometimes the other way around.

In the end, it becomes obvious, this is not simply imitation or coincidence, it is equivalence - everything is alive.

With every entanglement (correlation) being physical on some level (scale), it becomes obvious how a soul quantum of deceased relative can be temporary absorbed by your own before it is passed on to a next relative - it travels as a gravitational wave along the wormholes of dark matter filaments between galactic clusters of universes of smaller scale.

Now consider what happens when a gravitational wave is absorbed by the maximum. It changes (excites) its radius, affecting its gravity. This will cause real mass to move toward or away from maximum.

Note that this mass is, for the large part, moving perpendicular to magnetic field lines. So when it is in the form of ions, a voltage will be generated (action potential).

Now imagine that your brain maximum is absorbing waves of different scale (all harmonics are entangled), the only difference is in the energy (frequency) - or, the effect on your thoughts.

Knowing that these waves can be differently polarized, one cannot escape the conclusion that the function of a brain is impossible without the soul (maximum) and its constant coupling with other souls.

And that is why no one lives forever - one would be infinitely stupid and static (dead) without deaths, or more precisely, megadeaths, around it.

Be extending life artificially and preventing old people to die, one is disrupting the harmony of life. This is slowing down evolution of local life. Natural response is to speed it up and restore the harmony. This is one purpose of viruses.

How stupid is to wage war with nature - for it is a war between one ready to die at all times and one who wants to be immortal, even when it knows that immortal means utterly immoral, stupid, dead and alone. So far, so good...

5.2 Location of the soul

The least materialistic place in a universe is a naked gravitational maximum, therefore, in CR, I have defined the soul as such.

For Earth, I have established that the major gravitational maximum is at the inner core radius. In that case, the soul is localized at the centre of the brain.

Most likely, this is also the location of a soul [of a brain] in human brain - the location of conarium (pineal gland), although the soul exists independently of the conarium.

The fact that conarium is not isolated from the body by the blood-brain barrier system (unlike most of the brain) and is [cyclically] bathed in blood and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) goes in favour of the hypothesis.

Note, that the absence of a blood-brain barrier explains why the soul is greatly affected by blood content (eg. alcohol) and is the likely reason for hypothesized affinity of the soul for particular blood type.

The fluid Earth's inner core is suspended in is also blood, a large scale blood - magma and water (even if in siderophile form[10] - bonded with iron).

Note that iron, a major component of magma, is essential for blood production. This is common for all carbon life forms, including Earth.

Earth's outer core fluid is thus likely a superposition of blood and CSF (oceanic water, pH 7.33), which is not surprising, as the brain is still not fully formed.

5.3 Relativity of species

Every individual of any species is an ecosystem. This system can be very different from one individual of the species to the other. Division of life into species is thus highly relative.

This becomes more pronounced when the soul or souls of this ecosystem are taken into account.

In fact, considering that souls oscillate between different energy levels, it is appropriate to differentiate between species of bodies and species of souls.

Eg. a soul within the body of a bird or a dog may have previously lived within the human body. While the bodies are apparently very different, can the same be said for the souls?

After all, an electron oscillating between different energy levels in an atom is still considered the same particle [species] (although it too may oscillate between different body species).

On the other hand, muon is considered a different particle, even if it may simply be a vertically excited electron (and, even inside the atom, electron might be mass oscillating between electron, muon, tau and perhaps other states - eg. symbiosis with neutrinos and other electrons).

So does the soul change much in such oscillations, even if body does?

The answer depends on several factors:

- is oscillation in energy such that different states are of the same order of magnitude (horizontal oscillation), or multiple orders of magnitude (vertical oscillation)?
- what actually is the body of a primary soul, one containing most mental characteristics of an identity?

The mass of a human body is not significantly bigger than the mass of a bird or a dog - so this would be horizontal oscillation, with no significant changes in soul radius and mass (energy), most significant change would likely be in polarization.

The gravitational well (which may be polarized to some extent) of a soul has limited capacity, but the body mass of an individual [ecosystem] may be multiple orders of magnitude larger than that capacity. This is most likely the case in humans - the body of our soul may be limited to extremely small mass within the conarium area, and everything else may be organisms the soul is in symbiosis with - despite the fact that they grow and evolve together inside one distinct body, can we really claim *our* whole bodies as really ours, even if we believe we control them?

The feeling of control may simply stem from acts of synchronicity, and paralysis shows that we can lose control of most parts of *our* bodies which may also be interpreted as a loss of ownership.

Consider Earth's surface ecosystems - we often don't see all life on Earth as part of a single organism, even if it is.

Thus, the only difference between a soul in the body of a bird and a human body might be in the [mass] of organisms the soul is in symbiosis with.

Amount of intelligence may be the same, albeit with a difference in ratio between internal (introverted) and external (extroverted) expression.

Note that the amount of intelligence is not proportional to number of neuron cells or proteins. If 1 human can be effectively more intelligent than 100 other humans together, and humans are precursors of Earth's neuron proteins, obviously it is the quality of individual neurons that matters rather than quantity of neurons.

I find it likely that this ratio is proportional to the ratio of the soul mass (energy) and the mass of other organisms in the same body.

This makes humans more extroverted compared to birds and Earth extremely introverted compared to humans.

The amount of introversion might be reflected in the autonomy and/or complexity of the conarium even if it doesn't form the body of a soul - the avian conarium is autonomous and more complex than human conarium[11].

However, more likely, ratio of introversion to extroversion is proportional to ratio of glial (particularly astrocytes) to neuron cells. This would make the intelligence of elephants and whales highly introverted[12], compared to human intelligence.

5.4 The story below mushrooms (the story behind brains)

Fungi are one of the first complex organisms evolved on Earth's surface. They can survive and thrive in extreme conditions and their intelligence plays an essential role in sustainability of an ecosystem.

They communicate using electrical signals through their mycelium - a network of organic filaments (hyphae), but they also transfer chemicals (eg. sugars) between organisms. They can infect an animal and effectively take control of it, having a role of a brain in that, asymmetric, symbiosis.

Fungi with their networks are relative equivalents not only of the neural network and nervous system, but also of the vascular system and even the networks of the internet.

Perhaps it is most appropriate to say they are a superposition of neural and vascular networks.

Did we evolve from a fungus?

The similarity in control of organs by the brain and control of an ant by the fungus is, in addition to biofilms, another evidence that our organs have evolved, as hypothesized, from organisms in symbiosis - in this case, brain was the equivalent of a fungus, increasing its own abilities while subduing the intelligence of other organisms in symbiosis, effectively taking control of them.

What's in it for the ant? Security. Just like polarized people, it sacrifices freedom for security.

A nice summary on intelligence and roles of fungi[13] can be found at London Review[14].

Relative equivalents of fungi networks must exist on larger scales too. Evidently such equivalent exists at galactic scales, so why wouldn't it exist in Earth's mantle too, forming neural and vascular networks of the Earth?

Everything suggests that it does.

6 Conclusion

Life is a form of energy.

It cannot be destroyed nor can it be created from nothing. It can only be transformed and transferred through its evolution.

Thus, if one hypothesizes creation of life, one is hypothesizing a relative creation (conception) of life, the constituent elements of which, at some scale, must be alive.

A symbiosis of multiple organisms may have a unique soul, but it too could not have been created with symbiosis - in that case, symbiosis is the result of entanglement (co-evolution) of a symbiotic body with that soul. The entanglement of a body and a soul (gravitational maximum) is itself a symbiosis.

Everything is alive.

Each atom has a distinct soul (and is a form of introverted life), even if atomic compounds apparently do not.

I have previously stated that such compounds (eg. asteroid, a piece of rock) do not have a distinct soul (gravitational maximum). But this cannot be absolutely true over all space/time.

To conserve complete relativity, nothing can be dead or alive absolutely - only the amount of distinct life is debatable.

Each distinct form of energy should thus be entangled with a distinct gravitational maximum at least at some point in space/time.

However, if the amount of life cannot be absolutely zero, then a distinct maximum must exist at all times at some scale even in apparently *dead* matter (consistent with complete determinism and relativity of cause and effect).

This can be experimentally verified.

With increase in kinetic energy of a body, radius of this maximum must be inflating at a faster rate than individual maximums of matter, and, as each gravitational maximum (soul) has a spin momentum, the body itself will be gaining spin momentum converging to Keplerian velocity of space of this maximum.

Such maximum should then be present at each mass barycentre, with a

scale, generally, proportional to mass. The evidence for this could be supermassive black holes at galactic centres (quantum vortices), sunspots, etc.

While life cannot be absolutely created from nothing, it can be relatively - with the inflation of scale.

The inflation of the observable universe was the inflation of life and even life on Earth may have been inflated similarly.

In any case, the notion that life on Earth (or anywhere) has been created spontaneously must be consumed with a high degree of relativity.

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